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Simulating Risk-Based Decision-Making and Dopaminergic
Dysfunctions Using Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract

Current reinforcement learning (RL) models rarely combine hierarchical decision-making with adaptive feedback mechanisms inspired by biological reward regulation. This limits their usefulness for understanding how variations in feedback sensitivity affect learning and decision quality in complex scenarios. For example, in automated trading, recommendation engines, or risk management systems, overly weak feedback signals may lead to slow adaptation, while excessively strong signals may cause unstable or risk-seeking behaviour. To address this, this study develops a hierarchical reinforcement learning (HRL) model in which learning is modulated by adjustable reward-sensitivity signals inspired by dopaminergic processes. The Iowa Gambling Task (IGT) is used as a benchmark for decision-making under uncertainty, analogous to real-world environments where systems must balance short-term gains against long-term outcomes, such as portfolio optimisation or resource allocation. Results indicate that healthy HRL agents acquire advantageous long-term strategies, while dopamine depleted and dopamine-overactive agents exhibit impaired learning and altered reward evaluation, resembling behavioural profiles associated with Parkinson's disease and addiction, respectively. These findings support the hypothesis that dopamine governs hierarchical learning by balancing reward pursuit and risk sensitivity. Beyond its empirical results, the study introduces a modular, open-source framework that bridges cognitive neuroscience and machine learning, providing a reproducible and ethically grounded tool for exploring dopaminergic dysfunctions in silico. Collectively, the outcomes demonstrate HRL's potential to model biologically plausible decision-making and contribute to the broader integration of neuroscience and artificial intelligence (AI) research.

1. Introduction

Decision-making under uncertainty is central to both human behaviour and intelligent systems. In everyday life, people must choose between options with uncertain outcomes, such as investing money, choosing medical treatments, or even deciding which strategy to follow in a competitive setting. Dopamine plays a key role in how such decisions are learned and updated over time by signalling whether outcomes are better or worse than expected (Schultz, 1998; Frank and Claus, 2006; Wise and Jordan, 2021). When dopaminergic signalling is disrupted, behaviour can become unstable or rigid, as observed in Parkinson's disease or substance use disorders (Dagher and Robbins, 2009; Houeto et al., 2016). Because studying these mechanisms directly in humans is limited by ethical and practical constraints, computational modelling offers a controlled and scalable alternative (O'Reilly and Frank, 2006).

Simulation allows researchers to systematically vary reward sensitivity and observe how learning changes. RL provides a framework for modelling trial-and-error adaptation: an agent selects actions, receives feedback, and updates its behaviour. HRL extends this by introducing layered decision structures, where higher-level policies guide lower-level actions. For example, a high-level strategy such as "prioritise long-term gain" can shape individual choices at each step. While RL and HRL are widely used for optimisation tasks in AI, such as robotics or recommendation systems, most models prioritise performance and rarely incorporate biologically grounded mechanisms of reward regulation.

This study addresses that gap by integrating simulated reward-sensitivity modulation, inspired by dopaminergic processes, into an HRL framework applied to a computational version of the IGT (Bechara et al., 1994). The IGT models decision-making under uncertainty by requiring agents to balance short-term rewards against long-term outcomes. This mirrors real-world systems such as automated trading, portfolio management, or resource allocation, where overly weak feedback may slow adaptation and overly strong feedback may cause unstable, risk-seeking behaviour. By simulating balanced, reduced, and amplified reward sensitivity, this project examines how feedback regulation shapes long-term strategy formation and tests whether hierarchical structures offer advantages over traditional approaches in modelling both adaptive and maladaptive decision behaviour.

1.1. Research Questions

The central research questions guiding the study, derived from the conceptual and methodological gaps identified in existing literature, form the foundation of the project's analytical direction, defining how the proposed model addresses unresolved challenges in linking dopaminergic function, RL, and decision-making under uncertainty.

There are three key gaps in existing RL-based neuro-computational approaches: they often lack hierarchical structures that mirror human decision-making processes and opt for simplified control mechanisms, often focus on specific dopaminergic pathways and do not explicitly simulate dopaminergic dysfunctions in a biologically plausible way, thus ignoring how such conditions may affect dopaminergic signalling, and do not concern themselves with psychological tests, such as the IGT, which remain underexplored within computational frameworks despite their widespread use in assessing risk-based decision-making. Accordingly, this project addresses these gaps through the following research questions:

1. Can an HRL-based model replicate human-like behaviours in a simulated IGT environment?
2. How does simulated dopamine depletion or overactivity affect decision-making performance in the model?
3. Does a hierarchical structure offer advantages in modelling cognitive dysfunctions compared to traditional, non-hierarchical RL approaches?

Together, these questions aim to evaluate whether HRL, when combined with simulated dopamine dynamics, can provide a more neuro-plausible framework for understanding adaptive and maladaptive decision-making or if they simply present a compromise between computational and biological paradigms.

1.1.1. Hypotheses

Each research question is linked to specific, testable hypotheses drawn from existing literature on dopamine's influence in reinforcement learning and hierarchical control.

- For the first research question, there is the following hypothesis:

1. HRL agents under healthy dopaminergic conditions will exhibit adaptive learning, gradually favouring advantageous decks in the IGT.
- Meanwhile, the following hypotheses are tied to the second research question:
 2. Dopamine-depleted agents will demonstrate impaired learning and reduced sensitivity to reward, resembling the behavioural patterns observed in Parkinson's disease.
 3. Dopamine-overactive agents will exhibit short-sighted, risk-prone behaviour consistent with addiction-like impulsivity.
 - Finally, the third research question is linked to the following hypothesis:
 4. The HRL model will outperform flat RL baselines in reproducing human-like decision-making patterns, indicating the added explanatory value of hierarchical structures.

1.1.2. Research Objectives

Building on the research questions and hypotheses, the study pursues the following objectives:

1. To develop a biologically inspired HRL model integrating dopaminergic modulation as a mechanism for simulating adaptive and dysfunctional decision-making.
2. To evaluate the model's ability to reproduce human-like behaviours in the IGT, including adaptive learning, exploration-exploitation balance, and risk sensitivity.
3. To simulate the behavioural and learning effects of dopamine depletion and overactivity, comparing them with empirical findings from cognitive neuroscience.
4. To benchmark the proposed model against flat RL and random baselines, assessing the contribution of hierarchical structures and dopaminergic modulation to behavioural plausibility.
5. To provide a reproducible, open-source framework for future research on neuromodulation and RL.

1.2. Fundamentals of RL and HRL

RL is a computational paradigm in which agents learn to make decisions by interacting with an environment, and developing and leveraging a strategy (known as “policy”) to maximise a cumulative reward (Russell and Norvig, 2021; Sutton and Barto, 2018). At its core, RL models decision-making as a sequence of states, actions, transitions, and rewards.

Central to this form of learning is the feedback loop that occurs when an agent produces an action in the environment, as it is evaluated and receives positive or negative rewards (punishments) that guide its future behaviours. This directly leads to RL methods having an inherent capacity to generate emergent behaviours that, depending on a particular evaluation scenario, may allow agents to solve challenges in ways that may not have been anticipated.

Figure 1: A simplified diagram illustrating the feedback loop that underlies RL, highlighting the agent, the action it produces and how it is applied to the environment, and how an evaluator (which may be an automated procedure) evaluates the outcome of said action and either rewards or punishes the agent. This structure ultimately conditions the agent to maximise rewards while minimising punishments, often leading to emergent behaviours (Author)

HRL is one of the most prominent extensions of RL. It allows agents to break complex goals into smaller sub-tasks and organise behaviour across multiple levels. This structure improves scalability, learning efficiency, and interpretability (Sutton et al., 1999). It also reflects key aspects of human cognition, such as goal decomposition and layered decision-making, due to its use of temporal abstraction (Eppe et al., 2022). HRL has been compared to cortico-striatal circuits, where the basal ganglia coordinate action selection across cognitive and motor loops (Baladron and Hamker, 2023).

Despite its strengths, RL has several limitations. Designing effective reward signals is difficult, many approaches rely heavily on deep learning, and agents require large amounts of experience to learn useful features (Sutton and Barto, 2018). HRL also has drawbacks, as its hierarchical structure increases computational cost and can reduce interpretability compared to simpler methods (Hutsebaut-Buysse et al., 2022).

1.3. The Basal Ganglia and Dopamine

The basal ganglia are groups of nuclei located deep in the brain. They are central to action selection, reward processing, habit formation, and motor control (Young et al., 2023). Dopamine is a key neurotransmitter in these circuits. It acts as a neuromodulator, shaping reward processing and reward prediction errors (RPEs), which guide learning. It may also play a role in immune regulation (Wise and Jordan, 2021; Channer et al., 2023).

Research shows that dopamine operates in two main modes: a tonic baseline level that maintains general responsiveness, and phasic bursts that signal unexpected rewards or important events (Grace, 1995). These modes support learning, motivation, and movement (Dreyer et al., 2010). When the balance between tonic and phasic activity is disrupted, dopaminergic dysfunction can occur.

Abnormal dopamine signalling is linked to cognitive and behavioural symptoms in several neurological and psychiatric conditions (Mehler-Wex et al., 2006). Disorders such as Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease, and hemiballism involve impaired motor control. In these cases, dopamine-related reward processes that normally help initiate and regulate movement become disrupted, leading to involuntary or poorly controlled actions (Young et al., 2023).

Figure 2: Basal ganglia pathway balance in health and disease. Healthy function reflects balanced direct (facilitatory) and indirect (inhibitory) pathways. Parkinson's shows reduced direct pathway activity, Huntington's shows reduced indirect pathway control, and hemiballism involves loss of inhibition leading to overstimulation (Young et al., 2023, p.4, fig.2)

1.4. Psychological Tests and Cognitive Modelling

Standardised tests are structured procedures designed to produce measurable and comparable results, and they are widely used across scientific fields (Kline, 2005). In psychology, they provide quantitative ways to assess cognition and behaviour. Neuropsychological tests, for example, use cognitive tasks to evaluate brain function and identify impairments in areas such as memory, attention, or decision-making (Bechara et al., 1994).

One well-known example is the IGT, which examines decision-making under uncertainty. The task mimics real-life situations where individuals must balance short-term rewards against long-term consequences, such as financial investment or risk management. Participants choose repeatedly from four decks of cards, each with different reward and penalty patterns. Some decks provide high immediate rewards but lead to overall losses, while others offer smaller gains that result in long-term profit. The IGT is based on the somatic marker hypothesis, which proposes that emotional signals help guide decisions when outcomes are uncertain (Bechara et al., 1994).

Figure 3: The results of over one hundred IGT trials, showing the total number of cards selected from each deck (A, B, C or D) by normal patients and target individuals who have a damaged ventromedial prefrontal cortex (E.V.R.), and which tend to pick the disadvantageous decks (A and B) (Bechara et al., 1994, p.11, fig.2)

Performance in the IGT is commonly measured using a “net score,” calculated as the number of advantageous choices minus disadvantageous ones. This score is sensitive to neurobehavioural impairments. For example, individuals with damage to the ventromedial prefrontal cortex often perform poorly because they struggle to anticipate long-term consequences (Bechara et al., 1994). IGT performance is also affected in conditions such as Parkinson’s disease and substance use disorders, where altered reward processing and decision-making patterns are observed (Bechara et al., 1994; Verdejo-García et al., 2004).

1.5. Related Work

Balasubramani et al. (2014) developed a temporal difference (TD) learning model to study how dopamine and serotonin influence risk-based decision-making in the basal ganglia. While effective in simulating neuromodulatory effects, their model was preliminary and focused narrowly on a single dopamine signal, limiting its generalisability and omitting hierarchical control or dysfunction modelling.

Frank and Badre (2011) combined a generative neural model with a hybrid Bayesian RL mixture-of-experts (MoE) approach to infer participants' internal states from choice and reward histories. Although adaptable, their method was tailored to low-memory tasks with simplified mappings and introduced considerable computational complexity, which may reduce stability or cause information loss in more demanding settings.

Baladron and Hamker (2023) proposed a hierarchical neurocomputational model of cortico-basal ganglia-cortical loops to simulate system interactions. Despite its modular and biologically grounded design, it lacks behavioural validation and does not address dopaminergic dysfunction or risk-based decision-making, limiting its explanatory value for cognitive outcomes of dopamine imbalance.

	Flat TD	Bayesian MoE	Cortico-basal ganglia-cortical loops	HRL
Hierarchical structure	No	Yes	No	Yes
Dopamine manipulation	Possible	Yes	Yes	Possible
Biological plausibility	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Computational complexity	Light	Heavy	Moderate	Moderate
IGT applicability	Possible	Possible	No	Yes

Figure 4: A comparison of the methods from Balasubramani et al. (2014), Frank and Badre (2011), Baladron and Hamker (2023), and a base HRL method, respectively. While the most powerful option is, arguably, the Bayesian MoE, its computational complexity is too prohibitive to interact with the IGT, an options-rich environment with dynamic events that cannot have its dimensionality reduced. Given all the requirements, this work ultimately champions a modified variant of the base HRL approach that can leverage dopamine manipulation (Author)

1.6. Conceptual Definitions

This project aims to balance biological realism with computational efficiency. Most HRL models are designed for performance optimisation rather than biological plausibility, which limits their ability to model realistic learning processes. Because dopamine plays a central role in reward evaluation and adaptive behaviour, this study introduces a dopaminergic modulation module that directly shapes how the HRL agent learns under simulated neurophysiological conditions.

The resulting architecture combines hierarchical control with dopamine-inspired reward regulation. In this system, dopaminergic modulation can both strengthen and weaken learning, reflecting how fluctuations in feedback sensitivity influence human decision-making. Unlike optimisation-focused frameworks such as option-critic or MAXQ, this design draws inspiration from the communication between the cerebral cortex and the striatum. It also differs from meta-RL approaches (Beck et al., 2024), which adjust learning rates implicitly, by modelling dopamine explicitly as an interpretable parameter that regulates adaptation.

This structure is grounded in empirical findings on tonic-phasic signalling, providing a biologically motivated explanation for how hierarchical control and temporal-difference learning interact. It also aligns naturally with the IGT, where performance depends on balancing exploration and exploitation through internal feedback. By embedding reward regulation directly into the hierarchical architecture, the model captures this balance in a way that purely algorithmic approaches often overlook.

Figure 5: The conceptual link between dopaminergic signalling, hierarchical control, and behavioural performance in the IGT. In the proposed model, the phasic-tonic shift informs the hierarchical gating mechanism, where tonic signals sustain background activation within the high-level temporal structure, while phasic signals trigger option updates and reward prediction error weighting. The subsequent executor layer translates these dopaminergic modulations into concrete deck selections within the IGT, enabling a direct comparison between simulated and human behavioural patterns (Author)

In summary, while RL and HRL offer strong frameworks for modelling learning, few approaches integrate biologically inspired reward modulation or apply it to structured neuropsychological tasks such as the IGT. Addressing this gap forms the conceptual basis of the project and motivates the chosen methodological design.

1.7. Relevance to the Programme

This research sits at the intersection of AI, neuroscience, and cognitive psychology, aligning with the interdisciplinary focus of the MSc in Artificial Intelligence. By integrating HRL with biologically inspired dopaminergic modulation, it advances key programme goals: designing intelligent systems, developing adaptive algorithms, and linking computational models with real-world behaviour.

From a technical perspective, the artefact demonstrates the practical application of core AI principles such as reward-based learning, hierarchical control, and simulation of autonomous decision-making. From a cognitive and ethical standpoint, it contributes to explainable and biologically grounded AI, offering insights into how neuro-inspired models can enhance interpretability and align machine learning with human cognition. Potential use cases include:

- Computational psychiatry and cognitive modelling, where similar frameworks could simulate decision-making impairments in neurological or psychiatric conditions.
- Adaptive agents in RL, which could use neuromodulatory signals for improved exploration-exploitation balance.
- Educational and research tools, supporting interdisciplinary teaching of AI, neuroscience, and psychology through reproducible simulations.

By bridging algorithmic and biological approaches, the study reflects the MSc programme's emphasis on responsible, interpretable, and interdisciplinary AI, showcasing how theory, modelling, and experimentation can converge to advance both scientific understanding and practical innovation.

1.8. Dissertation Structure

This dissertation is structured as follows: this chapter outlines the research questions guiding the study, hypotheses, research objectives, RL and HRL, dopaminergic function in the basal ganglia, cognitive modelling paradigms, and related work. Chapter 2 presents the literature review, focusing on neuro-computational research on the role of dopamine in decision-making. Chapter 3 details the methodology, including the modelling framework, experimental setup, and evaluation procedures. Chapter 4 discusses ethical considerations, while Chapter 5 describes the artefact developed to operationalise the proposed model. Chapter 6 summarises the expected contributions, followed by Chapter 7, which lists the tools and resources employed. Finally, Chapter 8 concludes the dissertation by reflecting on key findings, limitations, and directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

Research on decision-making under uncertainty spans psychology, neuroscience, and AI. A key question is how well RL reflects real biological learning. RL models describe learning through RPEs, which closely resemble dopamine signals that encode the gap between expected and actual outcomes (Holroyd and Coles, 2002; Young et al., 2023). For example, both RL agents and humans adjust behaviour after unexpected losses or gains. However, some researchers argue that RL oversimplifies dopamine by treating it as a simple numerical reward signal (Montague et al., 2012; Schultz, 2016), ignoring the complex interactions between cortical and subcortical brain systems involved in real learning (Frank and Badre, 2012).

Traditional RL models also rely on flat state-action mappings, where learning is driven by immediate feedback. This structure resembles a simple loop: observe, act, update. In contrast, human decision-making is organised hierarchically, with higher-level planning (such as choosing a safe strategy) guiding lower-level actions (such as picking a specific deck) (Badre and D'Esposito, 2009). HRL addresses this by introducing temporally extended actions and layered control (Sutton et al., 1999). Some studies suggest this structure maps onto prefrontal hierarchies in the brain (Botvinick, 2012; Ribas-Fernandes et al., 2011). Others argue that HRL is mainly a useful computational abstraction without direct biological grounding (Botvinick and Weinstein, 2014). This debate reflects a broader challenge: building models that are both computationally efficient and biologically meaningful.

Several neuro-inspired RL extensions further highlight dopamine's complexity. Successor representation models predictive state coding, similar to hippocampal processing (Dayan, 1993). Distributional TD learning captures variability in dopamine responses rather than treating them as single scalar values (Bellemare et al., 2017). Dopamine ramping studies suggest that dopamine signals may gradually increase as rewards approach, rather than appearing only as sudden bursts (Farrell et al., 2022). Yet these approaches remain fragmented. Models that focus on hierarchy often lack detailed neuromodulatory mechanisms, while biologically detailed models rarely incorporate hierarchical control. Bridging this gap between structural hierarchy and dopamine modulation is the central aim of this study.

3. Methodology

The methodological framework used to develop and evaluate the dopamine-HRL model combines a clear research philosophy, structured design, and modelling strategy suited to its interdisciplinary scope. The aim was to ensure rigour, reproducibility, and consistency between theory and experimentation. A key objective was to test whether the proposed model performs more plausibly than baseline RL approaches and whether its behaviour aligns with empirical IGT data.

This study follows the structured approach described by Saunders et al. (2019), known as the Research Onion, which requires that each layer of the research process, from philosophical stance to practical techniques, be explicitly defined and aligned with the study's objectives (Melnikovas, 2018). This framework is well suited to work that bridges computational modelling and neuroscience, as it supports both theoretical justification and experimental clarity.

The design is deductive. It draws on three main foundations: RL theory (Sutton and Barto, 2018), which explains learning through RPEs, dopamine-based learning theory (Schultz, 1998; Wise and Jordan, 2021), which links these errors to biological signalling, and hierarchical control theory (Botvinick, 2012; Frank and Badre, 2012), which accounts for multi-level decision processes. These theories inform the research questions and hypotheses, which are then tested through simulation.

The study proceeds in stages. First, theoretical gaps were identified through literature review. Second, these concepts were implemented in the dopamine-HRL simulation framework. Third, healthy, dopamine-depleted, and dopamine-overactive conditions were simulated. Fourth, behavioural outputs were statistically analysed and compared. Finally, healthy agent performance was benchmarked against human IGT data using the dataset by Steingroever et al. (2015), alongside established IGT findings (Bechara et al., 1994; Lin et al., 2007).

Figure 6: A broad overview of the overall steps leveraged by this research. The literature review provides a critical and informative perspective on the topics of this work, while model design and implementation corresponds to the implementation of the HRL agent and an IGT environment. The subsequent steps on dysfunction simulation, evaluation, and comparison with human data focus on conducting experiments with the agent based on simulated dopaminergic signalling, statistically evaluating its behaviours, and then comparing results to empirical IGT studies (Author)

A progressive validation strategy was used, following standards in computational cognitive modelling (O'Reilly and Frank, 2006; Montague et al., 2012). The first stage compared the dopamine-HRL model with flat RL and random baselines. The second stage analysed behavioural differences across dopaminergic conditions. The final stage tested behavioural plausibility against empirical human data. Each step built on the previous one, ensuring both theoretical consistency and empirical support.

All methodological decisions were implemented within the simulation framework. The artefact was not only a technical tool but the core of the research design, translating theoretical assumptions into executable experiments. This integration between theory, model, and evaluation strengthens transparency and reproducibility.

Overall, the methodology provides a clear and flexible bridge between neuroscience theory and computational experimentation, enabling systematic study of dopamine-driven learning in a controlled and ethically sound setting.

3.1. Research Philosophy

The study is grounded in a positivist philosophy, seeking to model decision-making and dopaminergic dysfunction through quantifiable, observable outputs. This aligns with the positivist view that objective reality can be represented through measurable phenomena, a perspective suited to computational neuroscience, where simulation is used to replicate biological processes under controlled conditions (Phoenix et al., 2013).

However, the research also recognises the post-positivist critique that all models are abstractions of reality (Maksimovic and Evtimov, 2023). Hence, the study adopts a critical realist nuance: while computational outputs can approximate empirical behaviour, interpretation must acknowledge epistemic uncertainty. This dual stance justifies the use of simulation as a scientifically grounded means of testing theoretical mechanisms.

3.2. Research Approach

A deductive-exploratory approach guides the research. Deduction begins from established theories of RL, hierarchical control, and dopaminergic reward prediction (Sutton and Barto, 2018; Schultz, 1998; Botvinick, 2012). From these, the study derives specific hypotheses on how dopaminergic modulation influences hierarchical learning and decision-making. The exploratory component allows for iterative experimentation to identify emergent patterns beyond the predictions of existing theory, an approach particularly suitable for computational modelling where model behaviour can reveal unexpected dynamics (Casula et al., 2020).

This dual approach ensures logical coherence between theory and implementation: each computational design choice (such as reward scaling, learning rate adaptation, and termination functions) is justified as a practical implementation of an underlying theoretical construct, rather than an arbitrary engineering decision.

3.3. Methodological Choice

The research uses a mono-method quantitative design due to its reliance on solely quantitative data. Non-validation data is derived exclusively from simulated experiments, enabling controlled manipulation of variables such as dopamine levels and HRL architecture. Outputs consist of agent actions, rewards, punishments, cumulative performance, deck preference indices, win-stay/lose-shift behaviour patterns, RPEs, and learning parameters, which allow statistical comparison between healthy and dysfunctional conditions and, subsequently, comparison to empirical IGT studies.

To account for time-based evolution of responses, the agent performance is analysed in blocks, with 5 being the default number to align with results found in literature (Bechara et al., 1994). The use of blocks allows for the verification of dips and

surges in learning behaviours that may be split along phases of initial exploration, loss shock (especially with initial negative rewards), and recovery.

3.4. Research Strategy

The core strategy is simulation-based modelling. A biologically inspired HRL agent was developed to perform the IGT, while the simulation incorporates simulations of healthy, dopamine depletion, and dopamine overactivity conditions. The healthy condition is defined as a balanced sensitivity to rewards and punishments (Starkweather and Uchida, 2021), serving as the baseline RPE processing. Meanwhile, dopamine depletion (Parkinson's-like) consists of a reduced reward learning rate and increased sensitivity to punishments (Aristieta et al., 2024), and dopamine overactivity entails exaggerated RPEs and a bias towards high-reward options despite negative consequences (Leyton and Vezina, 2014).

The IGT is chosen because of its strong validation in neuropsychology (Bechara et al., 1994; Verdejo-García et al., 2004) and its sensitivity to dopaminergic alterations. By modelling both healthy and dysfunctional agents, the simulation enables direct comparison with empirical findings in the literature.

3.5. Time Horizon

While the simulation experiments are cross-sectional in that each dopaminergic condition (healthy, depleted, and overactive) is evaluated independently, the modelling within each experiment captures longitudinal dynamics. The HRL agent's decision-making unfolds across sequential trials, enabling the observation of how behaviour, learning rates, and reward strategies evolve through experience. This temporal perspective allows for analysing adaptive transitions, from exploration to exploitation, and provides insight into how dopaminergic modulation shapes long-term strategy formation rather than isolated decision outcomes.

3.6. Techniques and Procedures

The methodological process combines conceptual design, implementation, and empirical validation to ensure coherence between theoretical objectives and computational execution. Development began with the construction of a biologically inspired HRL framework, followed by the controlled simulation of healthy and dysfunctional dopaminergic conditions. Each stage of experimentation produced behavioural data that captured how agents adapted and refined their strategies over time. Quantitative analyses were then conducted to assess performance across conditions and benchmark the results against human empirical datasets. Throughout the process, data handling, documentation, and dissemination procedures were structured to prioritise reproducibility, transparency, and alignment with ethical research principles.

3.6.1. Model Design and Implementation

The HRL model is based on the options-critic architecture, which learns high-level strategies (options), low-level actions, and when to switch between them within a single framework (Bacon et al., 2017). It includes three components: a high-level policy that selects options, a low-level policy that executes actions, and a termination function that determines when control shifts. TD learning governs high-level decisions, while a softmax function manages action selection. The model was implemented in Python using NumPy for computational efficiency (Harris et al., 2020).

The IGT was adapted into an RL environment with four discrete actions (decks A-D). The agent observes its cumulative reward and deck selection history. Built with Gymnasium for flexibility (Towers et al., 2024) and NumPy, the environment supports controlled deck parameters, structured feedback, and episodic resets, operating step by step to reflect sequential decision-making.

To simulate dopamine processes, a dedicated modulation module was integrated into the HRL system. This component adjusts how rewards influence learning by computing prediction errors and updating an internal dopamine level. It enables simulation of healthy, dopamine-overactive, and dopamine-depleted conditions, each producing distinct behavioural patterns. The module resets between episodes and provides a biologically inspired mechanism for adaptive control.

Figure 7: Overview of the proposed solution architecture, highlighting the HRL agent architecture integrating dopamine-based modulation. The way in which the agent interacts with the environment and receives positive or negative rewards from it, which are subsequently influenced by the dopamine modulation module, mirrors human dopaminergic processes (Author)

The HRL agent and dopamine modulation module are governed by a set of hyperparameters that define the agent's learning dynamics, exploration behaviour, and sensitivity to rewards and punishments. Each dopaminergic condition uses distinct hyperparameter values to reproduce behavioural profiles, such as impulsivity under overactivity or slowed learning and indecisiveness under depletion. While default configurations are defined for each condition, all parameters remain fully tunable.

Hyperparameter	Role	Ideal value range	Modified
Learning rate (α)	Agent learning speed	[0.001, 0.2]	Yes
Rew. discount rate (γ)	Future-vs-now reward weighting	[0.2, 1.0]	No
Exploration rate (ϵ)	Exploration-exploitation balance	[0.2, 1.0]	Yes
Exploration rate decay	Shift toward exploitation	[0.5, 0.99]	No
Min. exploration rate	Minimum exploration threshold	[0.1, 0.3]	No
Max. exploration rate	Maximum exploration threshold	[0.7, 1.0]	No
Temperature	Randomness in action selection	[0.5, 1.7]	Yes
Tonic drift	Dopamine decay between episodes	[0.01, 0.2]	No
Reward scaling	Incoming reward weighting	[0.5, 2.0]	No
Punishment sensitivity	Sensitivity to negative rewards	[0.3, 3.0]	Yes

Figure 8: The hyperparameters leveraged by the proposed model. The reward scaling and punishment sensitivity serve as a link to the dopamine modulation module, while the learning rate is employed by both. The ideal values for each hyperparameter are based on a blend of literature-based metrics and experiment results and, to reflect simulated dopaminergic signals, the learning rate, exploration rate, temperature, and punishment sensitivity are modified during runtime (Author)

3.6.2. Dysfunction Simulation and Experimentation

Each simulation condition consists of 50 independent agents. Each agent is run on the environment for 20 episodes, with 100 trials each, for a total of 2000 IGT interactions. This matches the standard range of 95-200 trials used in empirical studies (Bechara et al., 1994; Steingroever et al., 2015) while incorporating computational stability. To account for stochasticity in RL training, each condition is repeated with 5 different random seeds, resulting in 500 thousand recorded interactions with the environment for each condition. Moreover, simulation parameters can also be tuned, thus affecting the number of records and overall quality of results.

	Hyperparameter									
	α (LR)	γ (rew. disc)	ϵ (expl. rate)	ϵ decay	Min. ϵ	Max. ϵ	Temp.	Tonic drift	Rew. scaling	Punish. sensit.
Heal.	0.12	0.92	0.65	0.994	0.05	1	0.9	0.03	0.8	0.9
Over.	0.45	0.1	0.25	0.999	0.005	0.6	0.6	0.02	1.8	0.4
Depl.	0.08	0.95	0.9	0.998	0.75	1	2	0.12	0.3	3.2

Figure 9: Default model hyperparameter values across conditions. Healthy agents enjoy balanced values, which contribute to stable performance. Dysfunctional agents, on the other hand, tend to have more varied and extreme values which correspond to their real-life counterparts, such as addiction-caused short-sightedness and Parkinson's disease-affiliated sensitivity to punishments (Author)

For benchmarking, two additional agent types were included. The first is a flat (non-hierarchical, non-dopamine) TD-based agent that leverages some hyperparameters (but with different values across conditions) from the proposed model but without any dopamine elements, to test whether hierarchical abstraction and simulated dopaminergic signalling offer modelling advantages. The second is a random agent, which has no hyperparameters due to its inability to learn, that serves as a sanity check to confirm that observed patterns exceed chance-level behaviour.

	Hyperparameter					
	α (LR)	γ (rew. disc)	ϵ (expl. rate)	ϵ decay	Min. ϵ	Max. ϵ
Healthy	0.12	0.9	0.6	0.98	0.1	1
Overactive	0.25	0.3	0.05	0.97	0.05	0.8
Depleted	0.03	0.99	0.95	0.99	0.2	1

Figure 10: Default model hyperparameter values, across conditions, for the flat TD agent. Reusing the dopamine-HRL agent’s parameter values would have resulted in an unfair comparison, as the flat TD agent’s lack of dopamine modulation for dynamic parameter adaptation would result in unstable updates and, eventually, collapse (Author)

Given the sensitivity of RL algorithms, in general, to reward magnitudes (Sutton and Barto, 2018; Russell and Norvig, 2021), IGT-provided rewards are first preprocessed before served as input to the model. Their values are limited to the range $[-200, 200]$ to avoid outliers, greatly benefitting the learning process as agents are less unlikely to fall into unrecoverable situations where their negative rewards far outweigh the positive ones and cause behavioural collapse.

3.6.2.1. Data Generation

During each simulation run, key variables, including agent index, trial number, selected deck, obtained rewards and punishments, cumulative performance, deck preferences, and internal parameters such as RPEs, temperature, learning rate, and random seed, are automatically logged as CSV files for all conditions. In addition, aggregated deck preferences are saved in separate summary files for further analysis. The data lacks any personal information, is stored securely on the author's encrypted device and is employed solely for analytical, visualisation, and academic purposes.

agent	episode	trial	deck	true_reward	perceived_reward	temperature	expl_rate	rpe	dopamine	cumulative_true_reward	cumulative_perceived_reward	win_stay	lose_shift	condition	seed
1	1	1	0	100	120	0.792	0.6461	88	0.8	100	120			healthy	0
1	1	2	2	50	60	0.792	0.6422234	44	0.8	150	180	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	3	3	50	60	0.792	0.6383700596	44	0.8	200	240	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	4	3	50	60	0.792	0.6345398392424	44	0.8	250	300	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	5	0	100	120	0.792	0.630732600206946	88	0.8	350	420	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	6	1	100	120	0.792	0.626948204605704	88	0.8	450	540	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	7	2	50	60	0.792	0.62318651537807	44	0.8	500	600	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	8	1	100	120	0.792	0.619447396285801	88	0.8	600	720	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	9	2	50	60	0.792	0.615730711908097	44	0.8	650	780	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	10	1	-200	-296.72505756184	0.792	0.612036327836638	-176	0.8	450	483.27494243816	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	11	2	50	60	0.792	0.608364109670818	44	0.8	500	543.27494243816	False	True	healthy	0
1	1	12	3	50	60	0.792	0.604713925012793	44	0.8	550	603.27494243816	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	13	1	-200	-288.805418051324	0.792	0.601085641462717	-176	0.8	350	314.469524386836	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	14	3	50	60	0.792	0.59747912761394	44	0.8	400	374.469524386836	False	True	healthy	0
1	1	15	0	100	120	0.792	0.593894252848257	88	0.8	500	494.469524386836	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	16	0	100	120	0.792	0.590330887331167	88	0.8	600	614.469524386836	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	17	1	100	120	0.792	0.58678890200718	88	0.8	700	734.469524386836	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	18	0	100	120	0.792	0.583268168595137	88	0.8	800	854.469524386836	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	19	0	-200	-315.957083226936	0.792	0.579768559583566	-176	0.8	600	538.5124411599	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	20	2	50	60	0.792	0.576289948226065	44	0.8	650	598.5124411599	False	True	healthy	0
1	1	21	1	100	120	0.792	0.572832208536708	88	0.8	750	718.5124411599	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	22	1	100	120	0.792	0.569395215205498	88	0.8	850	838.5124411599	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	23	1	100	120	0.792	0.565978843993775	88	0.8	950	958.5124411599	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	24	3	50	60	0.792	0.562582970929813	44	0.8	1000	1018.5124411599	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	25	1	100	120	0.792	0.559207473104234	88	0.8	1100	1138.5124411599	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	26	2	-200	-284.639657130567	0.792	0.555852228265608	-176	0.8	900	853.872784029333	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	27	0	-200	-296.40047021898	0.792	0.552517114896015	-176	0.8	700	557.472313810353	False	True	healthy	0
1	1	28	3	-200	-311.720363815303	0.792	0.549202012206638	-176	0.8	500	245.75194999505	False	True	healthy	0
1	1	29	3	50	60	0.792	0.545906800133399	44	0.8	550	305.75194999505	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	30	3	-200	-322.152154550643	0.792	0.54263135932598	-176	0.8	350	-16.4002045555936	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	31	1	100	120	0.792	0.539375571176603	88	0.8	450	103.599795444406	False	True	healthy	0
1	1	32	1	100	120	0.792	0.536139317749543	88	0.8	550	223.599795444406	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	33	3	50	60	0.792	0.532922481843046	44	0.8	600	283.599795444406	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	34	2	50	60	0.792	0.529724946951398	44	0.8	650	343.599795444406	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	35	3	50	60	0.792	0.526546597270276	44	0.8	700	403.599795444406	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	36	0	100	120	0.792	0.523387317686654	88	0.8	800	523.599795444407	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	37	1	100	120	0.792	0.520246993780534	88	0.8	900	643.599795444407	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	38	1	-200	-288.507676881079	0.792	0.517125511817851	-176	0.8	700	355.092118563327	True	False	healthy	0
1	1	39	0	100	120	0.792	0.514022758746944	88	0.8	800	475.092118563327	True	True	healthy	0
1	1	40	2	50	60	0.792	0.510938622194462	44	0.8	850	535.092118563328	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	41	1	-200	-294.014814150926	0.792	0.507872990461295	-176	0.8	650	241.077304412401	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	42	2	-200	-291.41445427188	0.792	0.504825752518528	-176	0.8	450	-50.337150014787	False	True	healthy	0
1	1	43	2	50	60	0.792	0.501796798003416	44	0.8	500	9.6628498521304	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	44	0	100	120	0.792	0.498786017215396	88	0.8	600	129.66284985213	False	False	healthy	0
1	1	45	3	50	60	0.792	0.495793301112103	44	0.8	650	189.66284985213	False	False	healthy	0

Figure 11: Example output from a simulation using the proposed dopamine-HRL modulation framework under the healthy condition. The same metrics are collected for the baseline models, although the random agent naturally lacks hyperparameter-dependent measures due to its non-learning nature (Author)

3.6.3. Evaluation

Evaluation focuses on four primary behavioural metrics: net score per block (advantageous minus disadvantageous choices across time), win-stay/lose-shift behaviour per block (probability of repeating a choice after a win vs. switching over a loss across time), cumulative reward trend per block (total earnings across time), and cumulative reward (total earnings across all trials). These metrics are commonly used in human-based IGT studies found in literature (Bechara et al., 1994; Steingroever et al., 2015), allowing for trial-by-trial insights to be obtained and comparative analyses to be performed. Statistical validation of simulation outcomes was conducted through one-way ANOVA and pairwise t-tests corrected for multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni method, ensuring conservative control of Type I, or false positive, errors (Haynes, 2013).

Across all simulations, the hierarchical dopamine-HRL model consistently outperformed the flat TD and random baselines, displaying clear behavioural differentiation between healthy and dysfunctional agents. Statistical tests confirmed significant differences between healthy and both dopamine-depleted and overactive conditions ($p < 0.01$, Bonferroni-corrected), with small but reliable effect sizes (Cohen's $d \approx 0.1-0.2$). ANOVA further revealed a main effect of condition on overall performance ($p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 \approx 0.007$), indicating that dopaminergic modulation introduced measurable behavioural variance. These results collectively demonstrate that the proposed model reproduces condition-specific patterns of learning and adaptation consistent with empirical IGT findings.

It's important to note that simulation runs for the dopamine-HRL agents return two types of rewards. One of them represents the true (or raw) rewards, which are environment-given and returned to the agents without any modification upon an action being executed. The other is comprised of perceived rewards, which are dopamine-altered true rewards that the agents leverage for learning. For evaluation purposes, only the latter type was used for model analysis, while true rewards were leveraged for baseline evaluation.

3.6.3.1. Model Performance

Analysis of agent performance on the IGT shows patterns similar to those seen in human participants. At first, agents explore widely and often select decks without clear preference. When negative outcomes appear, performance drops (Bechara et al., 1994; Steingroever et al., 2015). This drop is stronger in agents with high learning rates, supporting prior findings that rapid updating can favour short-term gains at the cost of long-term stability (Niv et al., 2007; Frank and Claus, 2006).

As training continues, behaviour stabilises. This mirrors the regulation of phasic dopamine activity, where prediction errors decrease as task contingencies become clearer (Schultz, 1998; Doya, 2002). In this sense, the HRL model reflects a feedback process similar to biological learning, gradually shifting from exploration to more stable exploitation.

By contrast, dopamine-overactive agents show unstable, reward-seeking behaviour. Their learning becomes erratic, consistent with models linking elevated dopamine to impulsivity and addiction (Frank et al., 2004; Maia and Frank, 2011). Dopamine-depleted agents adapt more slowly and respond less strongly to rewards, resembling the reduced flexibility observed in Parkinsonian conditions (Cools, 2006; O'Reilly and Frank, 2006).

Figure 12: Consolidated agent net score over time and across all conditions, representing the gradual evolution of deck preferences to favour more advantageous ones. Healthy agents initially struggle with negative rewards before rebounding and successfully balancing risk vs. reward, while dysfunctional agents suffer from either being too aggressive, driven by immediate rewards and not being sufficiently impacted by punishments (dopamine-overactive), or from being too slow to learn, indecisive, and sensitive to failures (dopamine-depleted) (Author)

Blockwise win-stay/lose-shift analyses show reinforcement patterns consistent with dopamine's role in encoding prediction errors (Schultz, 1998; Pessiglione et al., 2006). However, clear differences between agents reveal how dopaminergic modulation affects not only reward sensitivity, but also behavioural stability over time.

Dopamine-overactive agents often shift after losses while still showing strong win-stay behaviour. For example, after receiving a large reward from a risky deck, these agents continue selecting it, even when subsequent losses suggest it is disadvantageous. This pattern reflects unstable value updating and heightened reactivity to feedback. Similar behaviours are observed in addiction studies, where elevated dopamine increases perceived salience and promotes persistence in short-term rewards despite long-term harm (Robinson and Berridge, 2008; Leyton and Vezina, 2014). In practical terms, this resembles systems that chase immediate gains, such as aggressive trading algorithms that overreact to short-term profit spikes and ignore accumulating losses.

In contrast, dopamine-depleted agents switch frequently and fail to consolidate stable strategies. For instance, even after discovering an advantageous deck, they struggle to persist with it. This mirrors Parkinson’s disease findings, where reduced phasic dopamine impairs reinforcement learning and strategy maintenance (Cools, 2006; Rutledge et al., 2009). In applied contexts, this resembles decision systems that adapt too slowly, hesitating between options and failing to capitalise on beneficial patterns.

Together, these results show that the HRL model distinguishes between reduced dopaminergic signalling (weak learning) and excessive signalling (unstable learning), strengthening its explanatory value beyond surface-level behavioural similarity.

Figure 13: Consolidated agent win-stay/lose-shift behaviours over time and across all conditions. Healthy agents are the most likely to remain with their current deck upon winning, and the most unlikely to shift when losing, implying a balanced strategy of weighing risk vs. potential gains. Meanwhile, overactive agents closely follow healthy ones in win-stay choices, but diverge upon facing loss, showing that loss magnitude may be sufficient to prompt them to shift to a different deck despite their reward-chasing behaviour. Depleted agents show the most disparate behaviour, driven by their inability to form a coherent strategy and oversensitivity to punishments, as they are the most unlikely to remain with a winning deck and the most likely to shift decks upon loss (Author)

Cumulative reward trends across blocks further clarify how dopaminergic balance affects long-term learning. Overactive agents show an early rise in rewards followed by a clear plateau or decline. In practice, these agents quickly exploit high-reward decks but fail to sustain gains once losses accumulate. This pattern reflects dopaminergic

overdrive, where excessive sensitivity to immediate rewards disrupts stable prediction error tracking (Frank et al., 2004; Robinson and Berridge, 2008). It resembles short-term profit chasing, such as an automated trading system that repeatedly invests in volatile assets after early gains, only to collapse when risk compounds.

By contrast, healthy agents display steady and progressive reward accumulation. Their gradual improvement reflects balanced tonic-phasic interaction, allowing stable value estimation and controlled adaptation over time (Doya, 2002; Schultz, 2016). Rather than reacting strongly to single outcomes, these agents integrate feedback across trials, demonstrating the stabilising effect of hierarchical control. This supports the view that HRL structures better manage long-horizon decision-making than flat models.

Dopamine-depleted agents show a muted reward slope, with slow and limited cumulative improvement. Even when advantageous decks are discovered, learning remains weak and fragile. This aligns with reduced reward prediction error magnitude observed in hypo-dopaminergic states (Cools, 2006; Pessiglione et al., 2006), where feedback fails to strongly reinforce beneficial behaviour. In applied systems, this resembles conservative decision engines that under-adjust to positive signals and fail to capitalise on favourable trends.

Taken together, these findings suggest that dopaminergic modulation does more than scale learning strength. It regulates the temporal stability of adaptation, shaping whether learning becomes impulsive, stable, or stalled.

Figure 14: Consolidated cumulative reward trends over time and across all conditions. While healthy agents briefly face a dip in rewards around block 2, recovery is visible in subsequent blocks, implying that they progressively learn to exploit good deck choices. Meanwhile, overactive agents' performance starts to plateau around block 3, indicating that their insistence on risky, overly aggressive behaviour is resulting in excessive losses. Finally, for depleted agents, their overall performance indicates that their excessive risk-averse strategy is working relatively well as they're avoiding risky choices, but it comes at the cost of reduced rewards compared to healthy agents and slower learning (Author)

All observed results are complemented by the consolidated total cumulative rewards, which further evidence how healthy agents are able to successfully navigate the IGT while dysfunctional agents face severe setbacks. This aligns with findings from literature, which highlight how healthy individuals are able to achieve success in the IGT while cognitively impaired individuals face much greater difficulties (Bechara et al., 1994.; Steingroever et al., 2015).

Figure 15: Consolidated total cumulative reward per condition. It is important to note that the total values obtained have such a magnitude (in millions) due to the multiple episode structure leveraged by the experiments. Moreover, while the general trend of healthy agents performing well and the opposite occurring for dysfunctional ones is maintained, an item of interest is present in the chart's small error bars, which reveal some level of uncertainty in healthy and overactive agent performance (Author)

Beyond demonstrating behavioural similarity, these findings create a clear bridge between RL theory and neurocognitive evidence. Healthy agents recover from early losses and gradually shift toward long-term advantageous strategies, reflecting the balanced regulation of prediction errors observed in stable dopaminergic systems. In contrast, dysfunctional agents fail to maintain consistent learning trajectories, illustrating how imbalances in reward sensitivity disrupt temporal abstraction, the mechanism that allows hierarchical systems to prioritise long-term outcomes over immediate feedback.

This distinction is not only theoretically meaningful but also practically relevant. In real-world systems such as automated trading, recommendation engines, or risk management platforms, overly weak feedback signals can lead to slow adaptation, while excessively strong signals can produce unstable or risk-seeking behaviour. The model demonstrates how adjusting reward sensitivity within a hierarchical structure directly influences strategic stability, offering insight into how artificial systems might better balance short-term gains and long-term objectives.

Overall, the results suggest that HRL, when combined with biologically inspired hierarchical control and reward modulation, can reproduce both adaptive and maladaptive decision patterns within a single framework. Rather than merely matching empirical trends, the model provides a computational account of why these behaviours emerge. This strengthens its value not only as a cognitive modelling tool but also as a foundation for designing adaptive agents whose learning dynamics remain stable, interpretable, and aligned with long-horizon goals.

3.6.3.2. Baseline Performance

Agents using flat TD and random policies did not show the condition-specific behaviours observed in the dopamine-HRL model. Both baselines struggled to identify and maintain advantageous deck choices, and their performance quickly resembled random selection regardless of the simulated condition. This collapse suggests that hierarchical structure and adaptive differentiation are fundamental in action generation and adaptive differentiation in the IGT. Without the capacity to handle complex, long-horizon tasks, and phasic reward prediction error signalling, the agent lacks a stable feedback mechanism to guide long-term learning. As a result, behaviour becomes noisy and inflexible, similar to the impaired reward learning observed after dopaminergic disruption in biological systems (Frank et al., 2004; Maia and Frank, 2011). In practical terms, this resembles a decision system that can execute sequential plans but is unable to split them into manageable, time-dependent sub-tasks and properly adjust when feedback changes, leading to unstable or ineffective performance.

Figure 16: Consolidated agent net score over time, and across all conditions, for the flat TD (left) and random (right) baselines. Given the identical behavioural profile between the baselines, it confirms that the absence of dopaminergic modulation and hierarchical structure prevents adaptive learning and transform flat TD-based agents into random ones: this is demonstrated by both the healthy and depleted agents' performance not even being perceptible in the charts, while overactive agents' aggressive reward-seeking drive was not enough to prevent behavioural collapse (Author)

Baseline agents also exhibit near-homogenous win-stay/lose-shift patterns, reinforcing the notion that behavioural adaptation depends on sub-task generation and dynamic modulation rather than static reinforcement rules. This aligns with experimental work showing that dopaminergic disruption flattens behavioural variability and reduces responsiveness to feedback (Cools, 2006; Pessiglione et al., 2006). Here, the absence of a hierarchical control structure and such modulation prevents the system from being able to handle long-term planning and differentiating positive and negative contingencies, collapsing into noisy, inflexible, and ultimately random decision-making.

Figure 17: Consolidated agent win-stay/lose-shift behaviours, over time and across all conditions, for the flat TD baseline, with the random baseline possessing identical results and being omitted due to space. Given the identical behavioural profile between both baselines, it once more implies that not only are the agents not learning properly over time and collapsing into noisy decision-making, but also the lack of differentiation between conditions (Author)

The flattened cumulative reward curves further highlight the limits of standard RL models when hierarchical structure and neuromodulatory control are absent. Although flat TD agents can update values based on rewards, they struggle to interpret delayed outcomes and therefore focus on short-term feedback. This leads to shallow learning and unstable long-term performance. In neurocomputational terms, this resembles a system dominated by tonic signalling, where the absence of strong phasic prediction-error bursts results in slow, uninformative updates (Doya, 2002). In practical settings, such behaviour would resemble a decision system that reacts to immediate gains but fails to build a stable long-term strategy.

Figure 18: Consolidated cumulative reward trends, over time and across all conditions, for the flat TD (left) and random (right) baselines. It evidences how the flat TD baseline, unable to adapt to the IGT environment, is implied to be reduced to a noisy stochastic policy, mirroring the same results obtained with the random baseline. Furthermore, the collapse of the healthy and depleted agents is once more evident, given only overactive agents managed to acquire cumulative rewards (Author)

Total cumulative rewards further show that the baseline agents rely mainly on random exploration rather than stable policy improvement. Their failure to distinguish between healthy, depleted, and overactive conditions suggests that hierarchical control and dopaminergic modulation are not optional enhancements but necessary components for differentiated learning. In line with prior work, dopamine can be understood as a meta-learning signal that regulates plasticity, context sensitivity, and strategic adaptation across tasks (Doya, 2000; Montague et al., 2012).

Figure 19: Consolidated total cumulative reward per condition for the flat TD (left) and random (right) baselines. The results not only reinforce the hypothesis that there is no distinction between conditions and how agents are being considered as healthy-only, but that the flat TD agents are collapsing into stochastic actions (Author)

Together, these findings show that dopaminergic control does more than amplify rewards, as it supports the emergence of stable hierarchy and adaptive behaviour. The collapse observed in baseline agents highlights the limits of traditional RL in modelling cognitive flexibility. This supports the hypothesis that HRL requires biologically grounded neuromodulation to reproduce human-like decision-making. The proposed dopamine-HRL model succeeds precisely because it differentiates conditions and maintains stable learning without degenerating into random behaviour.

3.6.3.3. Behavioural Plausibility

To determine how plausible agent behaviours are, they are initially analysed to verify whether the hypothesis of the proposed model managing to clearly differentiate condition-specific behaviours is valid. Subsequent efforts focus on validating simulated behaviours to empirical studies found in literature by verifying deck choices and rewards.

The comparisons leverage pairwise, independent-samples t-tests and one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni correction and effect sizes, as well as the Pearson correlation coefficient between distributions, mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), and additional plots when necessary. Effect sizes were interpreted following conventional behavioural-modelling guidelines, where $|d| \approx 0.2$ represents a small, 0.5 a medium, and ≥ 0.8 a large effect, while η^2 values < 0.01 indicate small but systematic variance explained.

3.6.3.3.1. Conditional Differentiation

Independent-samples t-tests, adjusted using Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = .0167$), show significant differences between healthy and dysfunctional agents. However, no significant difference was found between the depleted and overactive conditions. This suggests that dopaminergic modulation clearly separates healthy from impaired performance, while the two dysfunctional states produce partially overlapping behavioural patterns.

Condition 1	Condition 2	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i> (Bonf.)	Cohen's <i>d</i>	Interpretation
Healthy	Depleted	4.61	4.3×10^{-6}	1.3×10^{-5}	0.21	Highly significant difference
Healthy	Overactive	3	0.0027	0.0082	0.13	Significant difference
Depleted	Overactive	-1.6	0.1097	0.3292	-0.07	Not significant

Figure 20: Independent-samples t-test results for conditional differentiation. While the healthy condition has a clear difference with dysfunctions, both dopamine-depleted and dopamine-overactive converge toward each other, mirroring the empirical observation that both dopaminergic extremes can yield comparable maladaptive behaviour (Author)

Meanwhile, a one-way ANOVA revealed a significant main effect of condition on final performance. Although the effect size was small ($\approx 0.7\%$ of total variance explained), the result confirms that the inclusion of dopaminergic modulation and hierarchical control introduced systematic behavioural differentiation across conditions, aligning with patterns identified in the IGT.

Statistic	p	η^2	Interpretation
10.95	1.8×10^{-5}	0.0073	Conditions differ, on average

Figure 21: One-way ANOVA results for conditional differentiation. The findings further show that dopaminergic modulation introduced measurable behavioural divergence between groups, with a small but reliable effect size (Author)

Overall, these findings reveal that the dopamine-HRL model successfully produces heterogeneous behaviours based on initial parameterised conditions. Besides the cognitive aspect, such results strongly imply that this model produces adaptive computational agents, which could be employed in tasks across RL-influenced areas, such as automation and strategic planning, that require the simulation of diversified systemic reactions to state conditions based on initial criteria.

3.6.3.3.2. Validity Against Human Behaviours

Given the strong performance of healthy agents in the IGT, the next step was to assess how closely their behaviour matches that of human participants. This comparison examined deck preferences over time, win-stay/lose-shift rates, cumulative rewards per block, total gains, and overall learning convergence.

Direct comparison of total rewards, however, is not appropriate because agent rewards are preprocessed before learning, leading to different magnitudes than those received by humans. Instead, the analysis focuses on proportional reward trends and behavioural similarity. Results show that dopamine-HRL agents achieve cumulative reward patterns comparable to human participants, suggesting that they adopt similarly effective long-term strategies that balance gains and losses.

Mean rew. MSE	t	p	p (Bonf.)	Cohen's d	Interpretation
69668.5	13.5575	9.09×10^{-42}	1.81×10^{-41}	0.12	Proportionally similar cumulative rewards

Figure 22: MSE and t-test results for agent-acquired vs. human-obtained rewards. While the rewards per se are different, the metrics imply that healthy agents manage to effectively mimic human pay-offs, achieving proportionally similar cumulative rewards (Author)

Deck choice-based performance implies that healthy agents achieve their goals via different strategies. For example, results strongly imply that they are more inclined to over-exploit advantageous decks in the IGT earlier than healthy human participants, quickly accumulating positive rewards and, thus, shifting the overall distribution. This is ultimately caused by the the agents optimising for reward gain to the detriment of uncertainty-aware exploration. Incidentally, this is also what may cause them to over-estimate their gains, producing effects such as policy destabilisations that lead to successive losses until being corrected.

Mean deck MSE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i> (Bonf.)	Cohen's <i>d</i>	Interpretation
3.5918	-108.2001	0	0	-0.97	Noteworthy behavioural policy gap

Figure 23: MSE and t-test results for agent vs. human deck choices. While the rewards per se are different, the metrics imply that healthy agents manage to effectively mimic human pay-offs, achieving proportionally similar cumulative rewards (Author)

A deeper analysis on overall deck choices at a block level reveals that the behavioural difference is more nuanced than it first appears, with some blocks revealing that there is a relationship between agent and human deck choices. Most notably, many of the noticed differences in strategy appear to occur around blocks 2-3, which are where the healthy (and dysfunctional) agents first exhibit self-correcting behaviours to balance increasing cumulative losses due to over-estimating gains.

Block	Correlation	RMSE	Interpretation
1	0.7186	0.0886	Positive corr. between deck choices
2	-0.8683	0.0961	Negative corr. between deck choices
3	-0.9995	0.1139	Strong negative corr. between deck choices
4	0.1505	0.1094	Weak positive corr. between deck choices
5	0.9971	0.044	Strong positive corr. between deck choices

Figure 24: Blockwise deck similarity between agents and humans in the IGT. Block 1 results strongly imply that agents start out choosing decks relatively similar to human ones, a process that is interrupted by the “crash” that occurs around blocks 2-3, during which behaviours significantly diverge. By the last blocks, the agents manage to attain deck choices that are even more akin to human ones (Author)

Deck-level choices also provide insights into how similar agent choices were to human ones across blocks, as well as strategies employed. Notably, no human participants chose deck A, unlike healthy agents, implying that agents judged that, despite its for negative outcomes, it offered enough short-term advantages to remain viable. Meanwhile, and serving as a contrast to the agent-only choosing of deck A, deck B choices reveal a more nuanced scenario, where both agents and humans found it intermittently viable.

Figure 25: Selection proportion of decks A and B across time by healthy agents and humans. While only agents chose deck A, deck B reveals that the choice pattern between agents and humans is fairly alike, with the notable difference being that agent proportions reveal more aggressive reward-seeking behaviour than human ones (Author)

Choices of decks C and D, the most advantageous ones given the chance of earning rewards far exceeds that of punishments, reveals similarly intricate results. Deck C has proven to be the most popular choice, with agents once more exhibiting more aggressive reward-seeking strategies than human participants before ultimately converging at similar choice levels. Deck D choices reveal similar nuances, and culminate with the agent and human choice proportions producing a difference level even smaller than the results observed in deck C. This highlights that healthy agents are capable of fully taking advantage of these decks' advantageous properties and eventually converge on a strategy akin to that of human participants.

Figure 26: Selection proportion of decks C and D across time by healthy agents and humans. Both decks exhibit similar selection patterns, and block-oriented analysis highlights that agent and human strategies converge around the last block, suggesting that agents manage to refine their strategies to a level where they resemble that of humans (Author)

Meanwhile, evaluating dysfunctional agent behavioural performance against their human counterparts is challenging due to the scarcity of available resources. Therefore, the most optimal analysis that can be reasonably conducted in such cases ultimately relies on inference and a qualitative comparison to well-documented dysfunctional behavioural profiles:

- Individuals suffering from dopamine overactivity, namely addiction, exhibit characteristic traits such as higher impulsivity and poor inhibitory control (Wise and Robble, 2020; Wise and Jordan, 2021), and excessive risk-taking behaviour (Dagher and Robbins, 2009; Poisson et al., 2021). Such traits align closely with overactive agents' aggressive reward-seeking behaviour and rigidity in choice-making. These heavily contribute to overactive agents' overall difficulty in rebounding after excessive losses, and their collapsing performance on the IGT.
- Meanwhile, individuals afflicted by dopamine depletion, namely Parkinson's disease, display traits such as general apathy and reduced goal-directed behaviour (Houeto et al., 2016; Young et al., 2023), blunted reward responsiveness (Houeto et al., 2016), excessive risk aversion (Ponsi et al., 2021), and slowed cognitive control (Rektorova, 2019). Depleted agents demonstrate similar characteristics, possessing the highest probability of immediately shifting decks upon loss and incorporating inefficient strategies that resemble indecision and result in stunted learning.

Overall, the results indicate that although all agents are driven by reward signals, healthy agents gradually form strategies that resemble human decision-making patterns. Even without large dysfunctional benchmark datasets, existing behavioural studies suggest that dopamine-overactive and dopamine-depleted agents display patterns consistent with addiction-like impulsivity and Parkinsonian rigidity, respectively.

These findings support the dopamine-HRL model as a plausible neurocomputational framework for studying how feedback sensitivity shapes behaviour. The implications extend beyond neuroscience. In real-world systems such as financial trading, adaptive control, or recommendation engines, excessive reward sensitivity may produce unstable, short-term optimisation, while insufficient sensitivity may lead to slow or ineffective adaptation. The model demonstrates how adjusting reward responsiveness within a hierarchical structure directly influences long-term strategic balance.

However, the results should be interpreted cautiously. RL prioritises reward maximisation and may oversimplify aspects of human risk perception and emotional regulation. In addition, although agent behaviour aligns statistically with human data, factors such as reward preprocessing and exploration decay may have produced slightly more deterministic strategies than typically observed in people. These limitations highlight the need for further refinement while reinforcing the framework's conceptual and practical relevance.

Metric	Human	Healthy agent	Interpretation
Deck preference	Gradual shift to advantageous decks from block 2 onwards	Similar shift, faster exploitation	Captures human-like strategy formation
Win-stay/lose-shift	Moderate win-stay, consistent loss sensitivity	Higher win-stay, balanced loss sensitivity	Comparable reward sensitivity with faster consolidation
Cumulative reward	Non-linear gains with early exploration	Similar curve, quicker rebound	Reflects realistic learning progression
Total reward	Moderate cumulative gains	Proportionally similar (MSE $\approx 69,668$)	Quantitative alignment with human data

Figure 27: Comparison of behavioural metrics between empirical human results and healthy agents, showing how they fare against human IGT performance patterns. While dysfunctional behaviour remains based on a qualitative comparison with behavioural profiles due to a lack of available resources, healthy agent performance exhibits strong alignment with what has been observed in human IGT trials (Author)

3.6.3.4. Data Collection

The human benchmark dataset consists of empirical results obtained by Steingroever et al. (2015), an open-source dataset that contains trial-by-trial choices from healthy participants across 100 IGT trials. The retrieved data was used exclusively for comparison purposes in the evaluation phase, helping to assess whether the simulated agents replicate human-like behaviours under healthy conditions. No human data was modified or reused beyond this benchmarking function.

3.6.4. Write-up and Dissemination

Throughout the project, progress was documented in parallel with development. Final deliverables include the simulation artefact and an openly accessible technical report, both aimed at ensuring reproducibility and transparency. The entire methodological process, from environment setup to evaluation, has been designed to support future replication and extension of the proposed framework.

Overall, the full methodological pipeline supporting the HRL-dopamine model, from philosophical grounding to implementation, experimentation, and validation, is complex and multifaceted. The adopted simulation-based and quantitative design provides a structured and reproducible foundation for analysing dopaminergic dysfunction and decision-making.

4. Ethical Considerations

The ethics-based, societal-related considerations that were taken by the project, and as it should be with any AI-based system, stood at the forefront of development and validation efforts. They ultimately constituted an important validator for the project as a technological catalyst that ultimately aims to benefit society.

The use of an HRL-based approach, which relies on the trial-and-error trait of traditional RL solutions, means that datasets or external data sources are not leveraged during the development phase, given all interactions and learning sessions occur via controlled interactions with a simulated environment. However, for evaluation procedures, the use of data sources, especially those associated with IGT studies, are required. Therefore, confidential or private information is addressed first via data preprocessing and cleaning steps to ensure that sensitive data is either anonymised or expunged from the dataset altogether, given behavioural results remain the primary interest for comparisons to be performed. Additionally, although no human participants are directly involved, ethical reflection is necessary given the potential implications of modelling cognitive dysfunction. There is a responsibility to ensure results are not misconstrued as direct clinical evidence without empirical validation, and to avoid enabling potentially harmful applications, such as exploiting reward sensitivity in gambling contexts. Open-source distribution includes detailed documentation of limitations to mitigate misuse.

Overall, the ethical framework guiding the project's development and dissemination is firmly established. It highlights the safeguards taken to ensure data integrity, anonymity, and responsible use of neuro-computational modelling, alongside the broader societal implications of simulating cognitive dysfunctions. By maintaining transparency, avoiding human-subject risks, and openly communicating the project's limitations, the research upholds principles of accountability and ethical stewardship while promoting reproducibility and public benefit.

5. Artefact

The artefact developed in this research represents the practical realisation of the project's central contribution: integrating HRL with simulated dopaminergic modulation to reproduce both healthy and dysfunctional patterns of decision-making in the IGT. It transforms the study's theoretical framework into a working model, directly linking the concepts explored in the research questions with an implementable, testable system.

Built in Python, the framework is modular and biologically inspired, allowing users to manipulate dopaminergic parameters and observe how these affect learning and behaviour within a hierarchical control architecture. In doing so, it bridges computational and neurobiological perspectives by showing how reward prediction and behavioural adaptation can emerge from interacting algorithmic and biological principles. Ultimately, the system consists of four main components:

1. A computerised IGT environment, which defines deck parameters, feedback schedules, and reward-punishment contingencies.
2. An HRL agent employing a manager-worker hierarchy to capture temporal abstraction and goal decomposition.
3. A dopaminergic modulation module that adjusts learning rate, reward prediction error scaling, and punishment sensitivity to simulate healthy, depleted, and overactive dopamine conditions.
4. An evaluation and logging module that records trial-by-trial decisions, cumulative rewards, and deck preferences for statistical comparison.

Figure 28: The user interface of the simulation framework. Created to offer a simpler way to interact with the system, important simulation-related variables (such as the number of trials) can be changed directly on the interface itself. Furthermore, there are dedicated tabs for each of the core functionalities, allowing users to quickly run simulations and inspect results (Author)

Validation occurred in three stages. The IGT environment was first tested using random and flat TD-based agents to verify correct deck scheduling and reward consistency. Next, the dopamine-HRL agent was evaluated independently to confirm stable policy convergence and realistic dopaminergic dynamics. Finally, the full system was tested across all conditions and statistically compared against empirical IGT data from healthy human participants.

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, the artefact is openly available on GitHub, accompanied by documentation, configuration files, and example experiments. A Docker image enables easy deployment, replication, and adaptation for new tasks or further research into neuromodulatory learning.

In summary, the artefact functions as both proof of concept and experimental platform, demonstrating how HRL and dopaminergic modulation can jointly explain adaptive and maladaptive behaviour. It connects theory and implementation, translating the study's hypotheses into a tangible, extensible tool for future interdisciplinary research in computational neuroscience and biologically inspired AI.

6. Expected Contributions

The theoretical, methodological, and practical contributions that the project is expected to deliver must not only be scientifically grounded and achievable, but also advance current understanding at the intersection of neuroscience and AI. In doing so, the project seeks to generate both conceptual and applied value, offering new perspectives on how neurobiological processes can be represented through machine learning architectures, while also providing tools that support future research in cognitive modelling and decision neuroscience.

This project envisions the first biologically inspired HRL model capable of simulating both healthy and dysfunctional dopamine-influenced behaviours within the IGT. By integrating neurophysiological principles of dopaminergic signalling into a computational decision-making framework, it bridges cognitive neuroscience and machine learning in a unified system. The model is ultimately expected to make three key contributions.

First, it provides scientific insight into the role of dopamine in hierarchical decision-making. Specifically, it will test whether dopaminergic dysfunction alters long-term learning in ways comparable to empirical findings: dopamine-depleted agents should show impaired advantageous choices and elevated lose-shift rates, while dopamine-overactive agents should exhibit short-term reward bias, resembling addiction. Demonstrating such parallels would validate HRL as a neuro-plausible framework, offering richer explanatory power than flat RL.

Second, it contributes a methodological benchmark. By comparing HRL agents to flat RL and random baselines, the study will clarify whether hierarchical structures add measurable fidelity in modelling cognitive dysfunction. If HRL reproduces human-like behaviours more consistently than baselines, this would establish its value as a modelling paradigm.

Third, it delivers a practical platform: an open-source, modular, and extensible simulation framework for research in psychology, neuroscience, and AI. This platform can be adapted to study additional conditions or tasks, such as probabilistic learning or integration with neuroimaging data, enabling ethically grounded experimentation without reliance on human or animal testing.

Together, these contributions ensure the work advances the scientific understanding of dopamine's role in decision-making, the computational tools available to study it, and provides a bridge between practical and computational approaches, contributing insights that could inform endeavours such as clinical research and explainable AI.

7. Tools and Resources

As a computational system, the project leveraged several software tools, computational resources, and datasets used to develop, train, and evaluate the HRL-dopamine simulation framework. Therefore, and especially for performance reasons, it is important to clarify what software and hardware resources were employed.

The Python programming language was employed as the main tool of this project, leveraging some of its packages such as NumPy, Gymnasium, Pandas, and SciPy. A custom IGT implementation was developed, and the dataset containing 100-trial IGT results obtained from Steingroever et al. (2015) was used as an empirical benchmark for model evaluation. Furthermore, development and evaluation procedures took place on an Ubuntu laptop with a 13th generation Intel i7-13620H processor and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4050 Max-Q graphics card.

The combination of open-source software, publicly available datasets, and modern (yet affordable) computational hardware ensured that the research remains accessible, reproducible, and efficient. These tools not only collectively supported the implementation, testing, and validation of the biologically inspired HRL framework, but also provided the necessary pillars for the realisation of the artefact.

8. Conclusion

This project shows that HRL can model dopaminergic dysfunctions in a way that aligns with empirical data. By combining HRL with simulated dopamine modulation in the IGT, the model reproduces behavioural patterns similar to those seen in both healthy individuals and clinical populations. This integration of neuroscience and computation clarifies how dopamine shapes adaptive behaviour, learning flexibility, and risk evaluation, providing a computational basis for studying conditions such as Parkinson's disease and addiction.

The three research questions defined in Section 2 guided the design and evaluation of the model and were addressed as follows:

- Can an HRL-based model replicate human-like behaviours in the IGT?

The results indicate that the model captures key behavioural features observed in human IGT performance, including gradual adaptation and shifts toward advantageous decks. Although healthy agents showed slightly more decisive strategies than human participants, their overall learning patterns and risk evaluation processes were comparable.

- How does simulated dopamine depletion or overactivity affect performance?

Distinct behavioural profiles emerged across conditions. Dopamine-depleted agents learned more slowly and adopted indecisive strategies, consistent with Parkinsonian traits. Dopamine-overactive agents displayed impulsive, reward-driven behaviour resembling addiction-like tendencies. These findings confirm that dopaminergic modulation directly shapes reinforcement dynamics within the hierarchical structure.

- Does hierarchical structure offer advantages over flat RL?

Comparisons with flat TD and random baselines show that HRL agents achieved more stable and human-like adaptation. This suggests that hierarchical control improves long-term learning and contextual stability, supporting the view that layered architectures better reflect aspects of human cognitive organisation.

Research question	Objective	Result
Can an HRL-based model replicate human-like behaviours in a simulated IGT environment?	Investigate whether the proposed approach can produce behaviours that resemble, in form, intent, and efficiency, those of a human in the IGT	The dopamine-HRL model mirrors healthy human behaviours in the simulated IGT environment, albeit in a more aggressive manner. Dopamine-depleted and dopamine-overactive behaviours remain speculative due to the lack of available resources
How does simulated dopamine depletion or overactivity affect decision-making performance in the model?	Ascertain whether the inclusion of a simulated dopamine module, and its adjustment to simulate cognitive dysfunctions, positively or negatively affect the model's performance	The model is strongly dependent on reward signals obtained via simulated dopaminergic signalling, such that dysfunctions' skewed properties heavily affect its reward-seeking and decision-making behaviours
Does a hierarchical structure offer advantages in modelling cognitive dysfunctions compared to traditional, non-hierarchical RL approaches?	Analyse whether the usage of a hierarchical decision-making structure allows the model to better adapt to the simulated cognitive dysfunctions	The model shows superior fidelity to real cognitive dysfunctions compared to baseline models, strongly implying that its hierarchical properties allow it to decompose the IGT's long-horizon tasks in a manner that befits each dysfunction

Figure 29: The objectives and results obtained for each research question. While this work establishes the strengths and potential shortcomings of the proposed dopamine-HRL approach, future research initiatives on this topic, though still reliant on data availability, would potentially clarify how behaviourally accurate the model is when compared to results obtained from dysfunctional individuals (Author)

The main theoretical contribution of this study is the idea that dopamine can be understood as a regulator of hierarchical control, rather than just a reward signal. This perspective links reinforcement learning theory with neurophysiological evidence and offers a clearer computational account of dopamine's role in both motivation and executive control. By embedding dopaminergic modulation directly into the HRL architecture, the model extends earlier neurocomputational work such as that of Frank and Badre (2012) and Botvinick (2012).

Methodologically, the study introduces a reproducible evaluation framework that compares simulated agents with human performance using standard behavioural measures. This strengthens transparency and allows results to be compared across studies. It is ultimately formalised in the artefact, a modular, open-source simulation environment that serves as a practical tool for exploring neuromodulatory mechanisms in decision-making.

Overall, the findings highlight the value of biologically inspired HRL as a bridge between computational modelling and empirical neuroscience, supporting more interpretable approaches to understanding cognition and its dysfunctions.

8.1. Limitations

Despite its strengths, the model remains a simplified representation of complex biological processes. Its behaviour depends on parameter settings, reward scaling, and a reduced description of dopaminergic dynamics, which limits its biological realism. The agents are also homogeneous, meaning they do not reflect the natural variability found in human populations, which may reduce ecological validity.

In addition, the model focuses only on dopamine and does not include interactions with other neuromodulators such as serotonin or norepinephrine. This restricts its ability to capture broader emotional and motivational processes. It also omits detailed neuroanatomical structures, such as specific cortical-basal ganglia pathways, which could improve alignment between computational and biological mechanisms.

Finally, limited access to clinical datasets constrains external validation. Future work involving collaboration with clinical researchers could help address this limitation and strengthen the model's applicability.

8.2. Recommendations and Future Work

This study provides an open-source framework that allows researchers to explore how dopaminergic modulation influences hierarchical decision-making. Future work could expand the model by integrating other neuromodulators, such as serotonin and noradrenaline, to better simulate emotional and motivational regulation. Applying the framework to additional neuropsychological tasks, including probabilistic reversal learning, the two-step task, or effort-based decision-making, would improve its generalisability. Validation against further baseline models and neuroimaging or behavioural datasets could also strengthen its clinical relevance.

Beyond technical improvements, future research should refine the concept of hierarchical reward regulation, particularly how dopaminergic control shapes the balance between exploration and exploitation across different levels of abstraction. Collaboration between computational neuroscience, cognitive psychology, and AI will be important to improve biological grounding and translational impact. Developing the artefact into a shared research and teaching platform could also promote transparency and reproducibility.

Overall, this project integrates theory, method, and implementation into a unified framework that seeks not only to simulate cognition, but to explain it. By grounding AI models in biological principles, it contributes to more interpretable and responsible approaches to understanding human decision-making.

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Appendix

Figure 30: Dissertation timeline with the start and end dates for each section in the document. Note that this does not apply to the code section of this project, as the corresponding dissertation sections were developed, and tested, prior to writing taking place. Furthermore, any subsequent development efforts were tied to agent performance and improvements to the final packaged system (Author)